

Shared Spatial Mobility Laws Across Human and Animal Movement

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Abstract. GIScience has made foundational contributions to interdisciplinary movement science, spanning geography, computer science, statistics, and physics. Yet two major domains studying movement, human mobility science and movement ecology, have largely developed separately, with distinct conceptual and methodological traditions. Recent works have called for their integration within an Integrated Science of Movement. This work contributes to that objective by testing whether the fundamental statistical mechanisms widely observed in human mobility are also present in animal movement, laying the foundations for a unified and reproducible geospatial framework for cross-domain trajectory analysis. Using high-resolution tracking data from multiple animal species, we implement a consistent processing pipeline and analyse canonical mobility descriptors such as visitation frequency, exploration dynamics, jump-length, and waiting-time distributions. Results show that animal trajectories exhibit the same statistical regularities identified in human mobility, including Zipf-like visitation patterns, sublinear exploration, and heavy-tailed displacement distributions across species and contexts. This work leads to joint modelling of human and animal movement, supporting transferable mobility models and integrated simulations

relevant to wildlife management, epidemiology, urban planning, and One Health applications.

Submission Type. Theory

BoK Concepts. [GC1] Geocomputation and complex systems, [GC2-5] Space-time dynamics

Keywords. Space-time dynamics, Integrative science, Movement ecology, Human mobility, Complex systems

1 Introduction

Understanding the dynamics of movement, its interactions, and its bi-directional impact on the environment is a central challenge in both human mobility research and movement ecology (Nathan, 2008; Pappalardo et al., 2023). This shared objective provides a foundation for unifying these two fields, which have largely evolved independently. Recent review works have called for the creation of an Integrated Science of Movement. This field integrates human and animal mobility research conceptually and methodologically by

drawing on best practices from both domains (Demšar et al., 2021; Miller et al., 2019).

Despite similar goals, the separate evolution of these fields has led to divergent concepts, metrics, and modelling approaches. Human mobility research is founded on the notion of universal mobility scaling laws, robust statistical regularities governing exploration, preferential return, and predictability (Brockmann et al., 2006; Song et al., 2010). These laws have enabled the development of universal mobility models with wide-ranging applications, including traffic modelling, epidemic simulations, and urban planning. In contrast, animal movement has largely been studied within distinct conceptual and methodological frameworks, often focusing on species-specific or environment-dependent processes (Nathan, 2008).

2 Methodology

We analyse high-resolution tracking data from 19 animal species, spanning mammals and birds across five continents. Movement trajectories are processed within a unified geospatial framework adapted from human

mobility science to enable direct cross-domain comparison. Trajectories are standardised using consistent preprocessing steps, including stop detection, spatial discretisation, and quality filtering. To reduce aggregation artefacts and ensure interpretability, trajectories are analysed separately across biologically meaningful seasonal or behavioural phases. Within this framework, we compute four mobility descriptors commonly used in human mobility research: (1) visitation rank–frequency distributions, (2) temporal growth of explored locations, (3) jump-length distributions, and (4) waiting-time distributions. All descriptors are evaluated across species, seasons, and spatial resolutions.

3 Outcomes and Evaluation

Across species and behavioural phases, animal movement exhibits the same fundamental scaling laws previously identified in human mobility (Fig. 1). Visitation patterns follow Zipf-like rank–frequency distributions, exploration grows sublinearly over time, and spatial dispersion is predominantly subdiffusive, reflecting repeated returns to familiar locations. Jump-length and waiting-time distributions are typically heavy-tailed,

Figure 1. Comparison of scaling laws reported in human mobility literature and estimated from animal movement data for (A) the rank–frequency distribution of visited locations, (B) the growth of unique locations visited over time, (C) jump length distributions, and (D) waiting time distributions

indicating heterogeneous movement strategies. These regularities are remarkably consistent across taxa, ecosystems, and movement modes, providing strong evidence that shared behavioural and ecological constraints shape movement across species. At the same time, systematic differences emerge. Compared to humans, animals exhibit weaker site fidelity and greater variability in exploration dynamics.

4 Challenges and Innovations

A critical finding is that mobility scaling laws collapse under sustained anthropogenic influence. In all cases where empirical distributions deviate from expected heavy-tailed forms, animal movement is directly constrained or structured by human activity, such as physical barriers (e.g., fencing) or externally imposed rhythms (e.g., feeding or herding schedules). These constrained regimes are accompanied by increased predictability, indicating that the observed scaling laws are not statistical artefacts but signatures of unconstrained natural movement.

4 Conclusion and Future Directions

This work demonstrates that human and animal movement share a common set of spatial scaling laws, providing a unifying statistical and mechanistic foundation for modelling movement across biological systems. At the same time, deviations from these laws reveal how anthropogenic constraints fundamentally alter movement dynamics and predictability.

From a GIScience perspective, this work advances a reproducible and integrated cross-domain framework for analysing and modelling movement trajectories, bridging disciplines that have historically evolved along largely separate conceptual and methodological paths. By establishing a unified geospatial representation and consistent analytical pipeline, the approach enables direct comparison and transferability of models across human and animal movement data. Future work will extend this framework toward predictive and scenario-based simulations, supporting the joint modelling of human and animal movement.

Data and Software Availability

The animal movement data used in this study were obtained from the Movebank, Euromammals-Euroboar, and United States Geological Survey repositories and are

largely open access. The full codebase used to conduct all analyses in this study is publicly available on GitHub at [redacted for review].

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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